

NARRATIVES OF SURVEILLANCE IN SPECULATIVE FICTION: UNDERSTANDING THE SURVEILLANCE DYNAMICS IN MARGARET ATWOOD'S *MADDADDAM* TRILOGY

Arisha Habib

Ms., Jamia Millia Islamia, India, arisha.habib@gmail.com

Abstract

The field of surveillance studies, in its modern form, started gaining attention of scholars after 1950s and began to gain increased academic as well as public attention after 9/11. Interestingly, in its early phase, especially in the 1970s and 1980s, the studies relied not so much on Foucault but on the literary works of George Orwell. Till date, political and sociological analysis of surveillance are more often than not presented in the surveillance state scenario of Orwell's literary novel, *Nineteen Eighty-Four* (1949). Several critics in this field have pointed out that it is the literary representations of surveillance that inform the masses and shape their knowledge and opinions about surveillance (David Lyon 2007). Moreover, they have also highlighted the importance of the link between surveillance and culture, and control and entertainment (Gary T. Marx 2009). Products of popular culture, therefore, have been given immense value in the studies of surveillance. Consequently, literature has become a valuable site to study the connections between surveillance and culture. This shall not only allow the bridging of the gap between the academic and popular discussions about surveillance but also provide a platform to understand the possible social and psychological impact of surveillance. Therefore, literary imaginations/representations offer versatile imageries and metaphors for comprehending the dynamics of surveillance. Especially in today's age of crisis for humans and non-humans (COVID pandemic, climate change, social injustice etc.), the rising surveillance cultures, technologies and practices invoke the importance of speculative fiction which provides new vistas of imagining surveillance in nuanced forms. Renowned Canadian writer, Margaret Atwood, is a master of contemporary speculative fiction. The present paper seeks to delve into the intricate narratives of surveillance within the speculative fiction genre, with a special focus on Margaret Atwood's *MaddAddam* trilogy. The trilogy comprises the literary novels: *Oryx and Crake* (2003), *The Year of the Flood* (2009) and *MaddAddam* (2013). Through the lens of surveillance studies, the paper aims to engage in a comprehensive analysis and unravelling of the trilogy's depiction of the corporate influence on surveillance along with its engagement with contemporary issues of control, privacy, and societal norms. Through this study, it is aimed to bring about a deeper understanding of the intersections between speculative fiction, surveillance studies and contemporary cultures of surveillance and their societal implications. Thus, this research paper is a humble attempt to make surveillance more visible and understandable.

Keywords: Speculative Fiction, Surveillance and Technology, Bioethics, Bio-engineering, Ecological